

Studies on the Dissociation Constants of Amino Acids in Mixed Solvents

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In order to throw light on the effects of different mixed solvents on the dissociation of amino acids, the pK values of a number of amino acids have been determined pH-metrically in methanol+water and ethanol+water mixtures of varying compositions. The results show that the changes in pK_1 values are smaller compared to those of the corresponding carboxylic acids but the decrease in pK_2 values are only marginal. It is apparent that the ratio of zwitterions to neutral molecules decreases as the organic solvent increases. The results also indicate that specific solute-solvent interactions are of importance in explaining the change in pK values.

In order to throw light on the interactions of amino acids with different solvents, the dissociation constants of some important amino acids (glycine, alanine, leucine, histidine, methionine, asparagine, serine and threonine) in mixed solvents, like methanol+water and ethanol+water mixtures have been determined. The results are presented in this communication. This may help us to understand the role of solvents on the dissociation constants and the specific solute-solvent interactions involved.

Experimental

The amino acids were purified in the way described earlier¹⁻³. Methanol and ethanol were purified and the weight percentages of organic solvents in the solvent mixtures were determined in the same manner as described before¹⁻³. The slight traces, if any, of water present in the organic solvents were neglected. The dissociation constants (K_1 and K_2) of the amino acids have been determined in the way described earlier¹. A Systronic digital pH meter with combined glass-calomel electrode (properly equilibrated in the appropriate solvent mixture) was used before taking the readings at 298 K.

Results and Discussion

The acidic and basic dissociation equilibria of the amino acids can be represented⁴ by equations (1) and (2).

The activity coefficient data of the different ionic forms of the amino acids in aqueous and mixed solvents are not available in literature. Also, neutral electrolytes if used, would increase the solubility of the amino acids, and form molecular combinations⁵ which may be pronounced in mixed solvents. In mixed solvents, the activity coefficients change⁶ due to salt effect (f_i) and medium effect (f_m). So, the use of neutral electrolytes is carefully avoided, as solute-solvent interactions of unknown magnitude are likely to mask the 'medium effects' of the reactions. The complications arising from the addition of excess neutral electrolytes in the determination of pK values have been well discussed⁷. Thus we prefer to work in dilute solutions so that the activity coefficients (for all ionic species including H^+) may be regarded to be unity, and 'medium effects' can be determined. The errors due to neglect of corrections, though small, are likely to be greater in case of pK_2 values, for obvious reasons.

We have utilised the data given by Pearsons and Rochester⁸ for the autoprotolysis constant of water in $\text{MeOH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixtures, and the data of Wooley *et al.*⁹ for $\text{EtOH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixtures (upto 60%), for the calculation of the second dissociation constants.

Thus, we have

$$pK_1 = \text{pH} - \log \left(\frac{C}{a - C_{\text{H}^+}} - 1 \right) - \log \frac{f_{\text{RH}^\pm}}{f_{\text{RH}_2^+}} \quad (3)$$

$$= B + \log U_{\text{H}} - \log \left(\frac{C}{a - C_{\text{H}^+}} - 1 \right) - \log \frac{f_{\text{RH}^-} f_{\text{RH}^\pm}}{f_{\text{RH}_2^+}} \quad (3a)$$

$$\text{and } pK_2 = \text{pH} + \log \left(\frac{C}{b - C_{\text{OH}^-}} - 1 \right) - \log \frac{f_{\text{R}^-}}{f_{\text{RH}^\pm}} \quad (4)$$

$$= B' + \log U_{\text{H}} + \log \left(\frac{C}{b - C_{\text{OH}^-}} - 1 \right) - \log \frac{f_{\text{H}^+} f_{\text{R}^-}}{f_{\text{RH}^\pm}} \quad (4a)$$

TABLE 1—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF AMINO ACIDS IN METHANOL—WATER MIXTURE

Methanol % (v/v)	L-Histidine			L-Methionine		L-Asparagine		L-Threonine		L-Serine	
	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₃	pK ₁	pK ₂						
0	1.75	5.96	9.11	2.29	9.02	2.29	8.70	2.21	8.99	2.23	8.99
10	1.78	5.95	9.09	2.33	9.01	2.35	8.66	2.39	8.94	2.29	8.97
20	1.80	5.92	9.11	2.42	8.98	2.44	8.67	2.38	8.97	2.39	8.97
30	2.01	5.87	9.09	2.60	8.98	2.59	8.66	2.56	8.99	2.51	9.00
40	2.21	5.79	9.10	2.75	9.00	2.74	8.68	2.72	8.97	2.68	9.00
50	2.33	5.67	9.12	2.90	9.02	2.88	8.74	2.92	8.92	2.82	9.04
60	2.48	5.65	9.07	3.00	9.05	2.94	8.78	2.95	9.00	2.96	9.08
70	2.75	5.52	9.09	3.20	9.08	3.16	8.85	3.20	9.01	3.19	9.10
80	2.79	5.44	9.12	3.50	9.11	3.42	8.90	3.54	9.01	3.51	9.11

Methanol % (v/v)	L-Leucine				Glycine				α-Alanine			
	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK _R	log K _z	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK _R	log K _z	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK _R	log K _z
0	2.44	9.50	7.63	5.19	2.34	9.72	7.73	5.38	2.39	9.72	7.80	5.41
10	2.60	9.48	—	5.03	2.57	—	—	5.16	2.55	—	—	5.25
20	2.71	9.48	—	4.92	2.63	9.63	—	5.10	2.66	9.80	—	5.14
30	2.83	9.47	—	4.80	2.66	—	—	5.07	2.70	—	—	5.10
40	2.98	9.48	—	4.64	2.90	—	—	4.83	2.97	—	—	4.83
50	3.15	9.49	—	4.48	3.18	—	—	4.55	3.20	—	—	4.60
60	3.30	9.48	—	4.33	3.36	9.78	—	4.37	3.46	9.90	—	4.31
70	3.50	9.50	—	4.13	3.50	—	—	4.23	3.60	—	—	4.20
80	3.79	9.51	—	3.84	3.64	9.74	—	4.09	3.76	9.82	—	4.04

Std. deviations range from ±0.01 to ±0.03.
K_R=Dissociation constant of ethylester of the amino acid.

TABLE 2—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF AMINO ACIDS IN ETHANOL—WATER MIXTURES

Ethanol % (v/v)	L-Histidine			L-Methionine		L-Asparagine		L-Threonine		L-Serine	
	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₃	pK ₁	pK ₂						
0	1.75	5.96	9.11	2.29	9.02	2.29	8.70	2.21	8.99	2.23	8.99
10	1.78	5.84	9.12	2.36	9.15	2.37	8.67	2.32	9.10	2.29	9.00
20	1.84	5.76	9.13	2.40	9.14	2.46	8.67	2.39	9.09	2.39	8.99
30	2.00	5.76	9.12	2.61	9.14	2.61	8.66	2.55	9.08	2.53	9.00
40	2.19	5.69	9.12	2.76	9.15	2.73	8.68	2.68	9.11	2.67	9.02
50	2.31	5.63	9.14	2.92	9.18	2.86	8.75	2.83	9.15	2.83	9.05
60	2.51	5.56	—	2.98	—	2.98	—	2.93	—	2.91	—
70	2.67	5.53	—	3.20	—	3.07	—	3.08	—	3.10	—
80	2.76	5.52	—	3.45	—	3.27	—	3.37	—	3.37	—

Ethanol % (v/v)	L-Leucine				Glycine				α-Alanine			
	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK _R	log K _z	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK _R	log K _z	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK _R	log K _z
0	2.44	9.50	7.63	5.19	2.34	9.72	7.73	5.38	2.39	9.72	7.80	5.41
10	2.53	9.55	—	5.08	2.55	—	—	5.17	2.53	—	—	5.27
20	2.60	9.53	—	5.03	2.66	9.68	—	5.06	2.70	9.85	—	5.10
30	2.80	9.51	—	4.82	2.70	—	—	5.02	2.79	—	—	5.01
40	2.96	9.53	—	4.67	2.88	—	—	4.85	2.97	—	—	4.83
50	3.13	9.52	—	4.50	3.05	—	—	4.68	3.13	—	—	4.67
60	3.26	—	—	4.37	3.38	—	—	4.35	3.49	—	—	4.31
70	3.42	—	—	4.21	3.58	—	—	4.20	3.61	—	—	4.19
80	3.68	—	—	3.95	3.73	—	—	4.00	3.91	—	—	4.89

Std. deviations range from ±0.01 to ±0.03.
K_R=Dissociation constant of ethylester of the amino acid.

where, *C* is concentration of neutral amino acid, *a* or *b* is concentration of acid or base, and C_{H⁺} or C_{OH⁻} is concentration of H⁺ ion or OH⁻ ion in the experimental solution (determined pH-metrically). It is well known that pH measurement loses its significance in mixed and non-aqueous solvents. In such measurements, we actually determine the meter-reading (*B* values) which with appropriate corrections (log U_{H⁺}) give H⁺ ion concentrations. The appropriate corrections were made for the mixed solvents using the method described earlier^{1,2}.

The highest concentrations of amino acids and HClO₄ or NaOH used were 1.0 × 10⁻² and 3.0–7.0 × 10⁻² M (except in the determination of the first dissociation constant of histidine).

The pK₁ and pK₂ values (pK₁, pK₂ and pK₃ values in case of histidine) at 298 K determined at different percentages of methanol+water, and ethanol+water, are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The pK₁ values of the amino acids in water determined by us agree very well with the values in

literature⁴ (mostly by the use of cells with liquid junction (with salt-bridge)), though slight variations exist. The use of (i) higher concentrations of amino acids and (ii) the activity coefficients f_{H^+} and f_{OH^-} from the results of pure HCl and NaOH solutions in the calculation of H^+ and OH^- ion activities, may lead to the slight variations mentioned. In calculating pK_1 , Edsall and Blanchard¹³ used the equation,

$$pK^* = pH + \log \frac{\text{amino acid hydrochloride}}{\text{amino acid}}, \text{ but}$$

made no correction for the concentration of H^+ ions dissociated from the hydrochloride, in the second term of the right hand side of the equation.

Very few determinations are known using cells without liquid-junction potentials, and this method also involves certain assumptions. Thus, slight variations in the pK_1 and pK_2 values are expected. The determined value (2.29) of pK_1 of L-asparagine, however, differs considerably from the reported value (2.02). Asparagine is known to be present as monohydrate, which is the basis of our calculations. However, if the concentration of asparagine is calculated not on this basis but as asparagine itself, then the pK_1 value comes out to be 2.07. The pK_2 values determined by us are a little lower than those reported in literature⁵. Edsall and Blanchard¹³ also reported that the measurements made in alkaline solution gave unstable e.m.f. readings.

A comparison of the pK_1 and pK_2 values in mixed solvents is not possible due to lack of data in literature. However, Edsall and Blanchard¹³ made some measurements in alcohol+water mixtures; their results are likely to be defective as they have taken the E_0 of 0.1 N calomel electrode to be 0.3353 V both in aqueous and mixed solvents. But E_0 is known to change with the solvent composition. No correction was made for the measured H^+ ion concentrations due to change in solvent composition, though they emphasised the need for such corrections in mixed solvents. We used $HClO_4$ instead of HCl, as $HClO_4$ is not known to be associated in mixed solvents. As expected, the pK_1 values of all the amino acids increase with increase in the alcohol content of the mixture, but the magnitudes of increase are smaller than those of the corresponding carboxylic acids, due to the 'dipolar character' of the acids^{14,15}. It has been found that the changes are greater in methanol+water mixtures compared to ethanol+water mixtures, though the latter have lower dielectric constants.

The pK_1 values were found to be linear functions of $1/\epsilon$ and the mole fraction of alcohol at low percentages of alcohol. However, the interactions of amino acids are seen to be different in different alcohols. It is quite likely that the 'zwitterionic' character changes with the change in the nature of the solvent, and at higher percentages of alcohols, the proportion of 'zwitterions' definitely decreases. The pK_2 values remain almost unchanged (a very

little decrease is observed) in mixed solvents. The pK_1 values of histidine increase, but the pK_2 values decrease with the increase in proportion of the organic solvents; the pK_2 values are found to increase slightly.

An approximate estimation of the concentration ratio of 'zwitterion' to 'neutral molecule' can be made in the case of glycine, α -alanine and leucine, taking the pK_E values of the ethyl esters of these amino acids ($NH_3^+ R.CO_2Et \rightleftharpoons NH_2.RCO_2Et + H^+$) from the works of Edsall and Blanchard¹³, and assuming pK_E to be approximately constant in different percentages of mixed solvents. The K_2 values for the above reaction, $K_2 = NH_2.RCO_2^- / NH_3^+.RCO_2H$, gives the ratio of the concentrations of 'zwitterion' to neutral forms. The $\log K_2$ values indicate that though the neutral form increases in mixed solvents, the change is insignificant enough to have any noticeable effect on the dissociation equilibria of the acid.

Though it is not possible to throw light on the specific solute-solvent interactions in absence of ancillary data, some attempts can be made in this direction. For reaction (1), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_i^0(1) &= \Delta G_i^0(H^+) + \Delta G_i^0(RH^\pm) - \Delta G_i^0(RH_2^+) \\ \text{or } \Delta G_i^0(1) - \Delta G_i^0(H^+) &= \Delta G_i^0(RH^\pm) - \Delta G_i^0(RH_2^+) \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

where, the various ΔG_i^0 quantities are the respective free energy changes accompanying the transfer of the species involved from water to the mixed solvent. The left hand side can be calculated from the $\Delta G_i^0(1)$ and $\Delta G_i^0(H^+)$ values determined in this laboratory^{10,17}. The results are presented in Table 3. The $\Delta G_i^0(1)$ values increase sharply from about ~30 wt % of alcohol onwards. The $\Delta G_i^0(RH^\pm)$ value is not known; however, $RH^\pm$ in water must be in the lower free energy state due to the solvation of the amino acids with a larger number of water molecules¹⁸. Now, the nature of hydration is known to change at about 34 wt % of the organic solvent, above which the amino acids are desolvated¹⁸ leading to a sharp change in $\Delta G_i^0(RH^\pm)$. Very likely, this fact is reflected in the change of the $\Delta G_i^0(1)$ values. The change in $\Delta G_i^0(1)$ may also arise due to a change from the 'zwitterionic' to the neutral form, but this is surmised to be small, the main factor being the structural changes in this region—the structure formation of water molecules due to the addition of alcohol on the one hand and the hydrophobic interactions of amino acids and alcohols on the other.

The solubility of amino acids decreases as the percentage of alcohol increases, and thus $\Delta G_i^0(RH^\pm)$ becomes increasingly positive. However, most of the amino acids studied result from the replacement of different hydrophobic and hydrophilic groups in alanine, leading to change to different extents in the $\Delta G_i^0(RH^\pm)$ and $\Delta G_i^0(1)$ values. The solubility of the amino acids in water are in the order, glycine

TABLE 3— G_i° VALUES* OF AMINO ACIDS IN DIFFERENT SOLVENT MIXTURES

Ethanol—Water Mixture																
Ethanol % (v/v)	L-Methionine		L-Asparagine		L-Threonine		L-Serine		L-Leucine		Glycine		α-Alanine		L-Histidine	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
10	0.99	1.47	0.45	1.53	0.63	1.71	0.37	1.45	0.50	1.68	1.02	2.10	0.80	1.88	0.14	1.22
20	0.65	2.48	1.00	2.83	1.05	2.88	0.90	2.73	0.91	2.74	1.83	3.66	1.77	3.60	0.48	2.31
30	1.84	4.54	1.81	4.51	1.93	4.63	1.72	4.42	2.07	4.77	2.06	4.76	2.28	4.98	1.41	4.11
40	2.66	6.04	2.50	5.88	2.67	6.05	2.51	5.89	2.94	6.32	3.09	6.47	3.31	6.69	2.49	5.87
50	3.57	8.09	3.25	7.77	3.56	8.08	3.40	7.92	3.91	8.43	4.06	8.58	4.22	8.74	3.18	7.70
60	3.95	9.48	3.96	9.49	4.11	9.64	3.89	9.42	4.69	10.22	5.94	11.47	6.28	11.81	4.32	9.85
70	5.20	10.83	4.47	10.10	4.97	10.60	4.95	10.58	5.58	11.21	6.80	12.43	6.96	12.59	5.24	10.87
80	6.62	12.15	5.61	11.14	6.62	12.15	6.49	12.02	7.08	12.61	7.94	13.47	7.67	13.20	6.68	11.21

Methanol—Water Mixture																
Methanol % (v/v)	L-Methionine		L-Asparagine		L-Threonine		L-Serine		L-Leucine		α-Alanine		Glycine		L-Histidine	
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
10	0.21	0.83	0.37	0.98	0.49	1.10	0.37	1.68	0.91	1.52	0.91	1.52	1.32	1.93	0.15	0.78
20	0.75	2.01	0.89	2.17	1.00	2.26	0.90	2.16	1.53	2.79	1.54	2.80	1.66	2.92	0.30	1.56
30	1.75	3.50	1.72	3.47	2.03	3.78	1.62	3.37	2.23	3.93	1.87	3.62	1.83	3.58	1.49	3.24
40	2.64	4.82	2.60	4.78	2.89	5.07	2.58	4.76	3.10	5.28	3.37	5.55	3.20	5.33	2.62	4.80
50	3.46	6.63	3.38	6.55	3.78	6.95	3.39	6.56	4.03	7.20	4.62	7.79	4.80	7.97	3.30	6.47
60	4.03	7.99	3.70	7.66	4.23	8.19	4.14	8.10	4.89	8.85	6.11	9.07	5.83	9.79	4.15	8.11
70	5.30	10.12	5.00	9.92	5.65	10.57	5.49	10.41	6.05	10.97	6.91	11.83	6.62	11.54	5.67	10.59
80	6.91	12.43	6.48	12.00	7.60	13.12	7.32	12.84	7.68	13.20	7.92	13.44	7.42	12.94	6.95	11.45

* (1) = $\Delta G_i^{\circ} = \Delta G_i^{\circ} - \Delta G_w^{\circ}$, (2) = $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}^{\pm}) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_3^{\pm})$ [unit,].

>alanine>leucine (in the order of increasing hydrophobic character of the substituted groups). This would mean a reversal of solubilities in alcohol + water mixtures of increasing alcohol content. The extent of solubility has an important significance, as is evident from the $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(1)$ values of serine and threonine which have hydroxyl groups, and arginine and histidine which have amide and imidazole groups. From equation (8), it is seen that the magnitude of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}_3^{\pm})$ would vary with that of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}^{\pm})$, and would probably be slightly negative, on the basis of the above conjectured increasing positive values of $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}^{\pm})$. Similarly, for reaction (2), we have

$$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{R}^-) = \Delta G^{\circ}(2) - \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{H}^+) + \Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{RH}^{\pm}) \quad (9)$$

$\Delta G_i^{\circ}(2)$ is seen to change very slightly, and whatever be its value $\Delta G_i^{\circ}(\text{R}^-)$ should be increasingly positive as observed also in the case of most the anions¹⁰, i.e. transfer of R^- should be highly unfavourable as the organic solvent increases.

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